

Perspectives in school level planning and implementation for school improvement in Ghanaian Junior High Schools

Mark Quansah

¹*Department of Educational Administration and Management, University of Education, Winneba, Ghana, mquansah@uew.edu.gh

*Corresponding author: mquansah@uew.edu.gh

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19696376>

Received: November 10, 2025 | Accepted: February 13, 2026 | Published: April 21, 2026

ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore diverse perspectives on school level planning and implementation for school improvement and their associated challenges in Ghanaian Junior High Schools (JHSs). The study being conducted in a single Ghanaian district employed a qualitative case study design within an interpretive paradigm. The study's population consists of headteachers, teachers, School Management Committee (SMC) Chairpersons, school improvement support officers (SISOs), and a planning officer. From this population, a sample of 19 was selected employing the maximum variation variant of the purposive sampling technique. The sample includes 5 headteachers, 5 teachers, 5 SISOs, 1 planning officer, and 3 SMC chairpersons. Semi-structured interview guides were used for data gathering, and the data were subjected to thematic analysis. The study found that schools did not follow standardized planning and implementation procedures coupled with limited autonomy in planning, which affects the quality of plans developed by schools and the success rate of implementation. Furthermore, stakeholder commitment to planning and implementation emerged as a key challenge to the planning and implementation of school improvement programmes. Parents and SMC members had little time for the school and exhibited a feeble understanding of educational policies, which affected their level of participation in the school's affairs. The study therefore recommends that Ghanaian Junior High Schools need to formalize their planning and implementation practices and learn to adopt best practices in implementation. Finally, the government needs to reduce its influence in the schools' planning and implementation functions to make the schools more effective.

Keywords: Case study, Challenges in planning and implementation, Perspectives, School improvement, School level planning and implementation

1. INTRODUCTION

When schools turn around and experience improvement, a key element resulting to this has usually been the existence of a formalized process of goal setting and strategic planning (Strunk, Marsh, Bush-Mecenas & Duque, 2016). Armstrong (1982) indicated that the formal planning process requires organizations to specify their goals and objectives, generate strategies to pursue these goals, determine and implement structures to monitor progress toward objectives, and seek commitment from stakeholders. This planning process produces a "school plan" that outlines the school's goals for improvement and the strategies the staff will use to achieve the goals (Fernandez, 2011).

Furthermore, school improvement has gained much attention in a number of educational discourses across the globe. This is because the quality of school improvement practices establishes the justification for any investment made into education. In Ghana, a number of school improvement programmes have been introduced to make schools more effective. Mention can be made of the introduction of the Ghana Accountability for Learning Outcome Project (GALOP), Korea International Cooperation Agency (KOICA) intervention, the Professional Learning Community (PLC), Capitation Grant, and School Feeding Programme. These are national programmes but schools need to tailor their action plans towards these interventions. However, how schools plan and the quality of their plans have not received the needed attention from regulators. Strunk, Marsh, Bush-Mecenas and Duque (2016) emphasized that a common strategy employed in school improvement efforts is a mandated process of formal planning, yet little is known about the quality of plans or the relationship between plan quality and implementation. Their study found positive relationships between plan quality and

implementation outcomes. This is a good reason for schools to take planning and implementation of school improvement programmes seriously. Yet, not only is planning in Ghanaian schools not receiving the needed attention, but also the implementation. Schools that develop good plans also do not have the needed financial and political support to implement their plans. In recent times, a number of school improvement programmes in Ghana are nationally determined, making them top-down in orientation. Meanwhile, Sinay and Ryan (2016) stated that goals must not simply be top-down, since top-down goals usually have marginal success. Programmes sent from above mean the school's staff have been reduced to mere implementers. The result is the phenomenon of unresponsive school improvement programmes to schools' contexts.

Meanwhile, Thompson (2018) admitted the discrepancies in school contexts and realities, which made him decry the existing system-wide planning predicated on a "one size fits all" philosophy of planning for schools. Thompson therefore suggested that there was a need for a shift from 'mass planning' to contextual and individualized planning in schools. It has been seven years since Thompson's observation, but the planning and implementation regimes in schools in a number of countries, especially Ghana, have not improved much. This phenomenon has been the focus of this study, to explore the nature of school improvement planning and implementation in Ghanaian Junior High Schools and stakeholder challenges in planning and implementing school improvement programmes in Ghanaian Junior High Schools. In these two broader themes, the agenda had been to unravel the planning and implementation experiences of schools and the implications of such for their current forms or performance. To address this problem, two overriding research questions have been posited: (1) What is the nature of school improvement planning and implementation in Ghanaian Junior High Schools? (2) What challenges do stakeholders face in planning and implementing school improvement programmes in Ghanaian Junior High Schools?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review is focused on the two research questions of the study: (1) What is the nature of school improvement planning and implementation in Ghanaian Junior High Schools? (2) What challenges do stakeholders face in planning and implementing school improvement programmes in Ghanaian Junior High Schools? From these two questions, a central concept has been derived to drive the empirical review: Nature and Challenges of School Improvement Planning and Implementation. This central concept has also been discussed in the light of the systems theory underpinning the study to consolidate the theoretical foundation of this study.

Theoretical underpinning

In this study, the school is seen as an organ with interrelated parts playing roles that are to be harmonized for the improvement of the school. Planning and implementation, which are parts of the school's mandate, are expected to touch on all aspects of the school and must be done collaboratively by the key stakeholders of the school. This theoretical perspective of the study is in line with the systems theory, which considers the school as a complex system with interconnected parts (students, teachers, administrators, curriculum, etc.). In the context of this study, these interconnected parts may include teachers, headteachers, School Management Committee (SMC) Chairpersons, Planning Officers, and School Improvement Support Officers (SISOs).

The systems theory underpins this study because it presents a valuable framework for enhancing school improvement planning and implementation practices by highlighting the interconnectedness of various components within the educational system. Furthermore, the systems theory provides a structured approach to school improvement planning and implementation by promoting a holistic understanding, identifying critical connections, leveraging feedback mechanisms, fostering systemic change, facilitating complex problem-solving, and encouraging collaboration. The ideals of the systems theory are at least significant for this study, in one sense, thus, the overall emphasis on the need for collaboration in planning and implementation of school improvement programmes. This had also been emphasized by Thompson (2018) when he called for a school improvement strategy that entailed school-based planning and implementation done within the context of collaboration among stakeholders.

Nature and Challenges of School Improvement Planning and Implementation

Thompson (2018) defined school improvement planning as a strategic planning process by which members of the school community conduct a thorough evaluation of their school's educational programme and performance in the previous school years and develop a written plan that establishes the starting point for ongoing evaluation of efforts to achieve improvements in student outcomes in succeeding years. In addition, developing and implementing school improvement plans is a common undertaking for school administrators (Fernandez, 2011; Strunk, Marsh, Bush-Mecenas, & Duque, 2016) and has been a critical part of school leadership for decades (Huber & Conway, 2015; Meyers & VanGronigen, 2019).

As a complex process, school improvement does not have a specific checklist of factors that will result in improved student learning outcomes (Hamdan & Fradi, 2023). Nevertheless, the role of planning as a critical element in school improvement and effectiveness has taken a prominent position in a number of school improvement studies (Strunk, Marsh,

Bush-Mecenas & Duque, 2016). A number of these studies, especially those conducted between the 1980s and 1990s, raised questions about the quality of planning and implementation of school improvement programmes (Broadhead, Cuckle, Hodgson, & Dunford, 1996; Clark & McCarthy, 1983; Conley, 1993; Levine & Leibert, 1987). These studies generally identified that school improvement plans were overly optimistic, unrealistic, and lacking in necessary strategy and implementation details. The phenomenon does not seem to have improved much in recent times. To achieve desired outcomes through school improvement planning, it should follow a step-by-step approach that emphasizes data-driven decision-making, stakeholder involvement, and professional development (Hamdan and Fradi, 2023). They stressed that this approach would be very effective if accompanied by effective self-evaluation and monitoring progress.

Moreover, in Ghana, school improvement planning and implementation are usually focused on existing interventions or school improvement programmes. Kalman (2020) opined that the school improvement planning process should be evidence-informed, leading to interventions, actions, and strategies, followed by targets, measures, and outcomes. Abreh (2017) observed that the School Performance Improvement Plan (SPIP) has become an integral part of the life of public basic schools in Ghana. In fact, the SPIP was developed as a planning framework to guide schools in their school improvement planning. So, to understand the nature of school improvement planning and implementation at the school level in Ghana, it is important to explore the preparation of the SPIP, since it happens to be the key platform for Ghanaian school stakeholders to engage in planning and implementation for school improvement. A study conducted by Kwaah and Ampiah (2018) provides a comprehensive account of the nature of school improvement planning and implementation in the context of the SPIP. The preparation of the SPIP was a requirement that enabled schools to access the Capitation Grant for Ghanaian Basic Schools. Once the Capitation Grant was released to schools, the SPIP enabled schools to allocate resources to various aspects of the school to initiate the needed improvement.

Furthermore, Kwaah and Ampiah (2018) emphasized that the preparation of the SPIP went through the following steps:

1. Fixing a date convenient for stakeholders to discuss the SPIP,
2. Listing items needed by the school,
3. Estimating the total cost of items to be bought and other expenditures,
4. Vetting and signing of the SPIP by the SISO (School Improvement Support Officer, SMC, head teacher, and staff secretary),
5. Submit the final SPIP to the District Education Office for approval.

The steps above indicate that school improvement planning within the context of the SPIP is systematic, collaborative, and possesses the internal mechanism for accountability. This is in line with the tenets of the Systems Theory, which generally highlight the interconnectedness of various components within the school. Furthermore, the SPIP was not prepared by one person due to the need for collaboration in the planning process, and this aligns with the systems theory's emphasis on collaboration. Additionally, during the listing of the items, the stakeholders usually focused on the areas of the school that needed immediate attention. This usually generated arguments that delayed the entire planning process because the school's needs outweighed the Capitation Grant released to the school. Additionally, Kwaah and Ampiah (2018) observed a mismatch between the needs of the schools and the budget prepared in the form of the SPIP. Thus, sometimes, schools did not strictly adhere to the items on the SPIP. Similarly, Abreh (2017) observed that a number of schools in Ghana could not achieve about half of the activities listed in the SPIP, due to either the delay of arrival or the unavailability of the capitation grants. He blamed the incompleteness of activities on the rising costs of budgeted items caused by the delays in the arrival of the grants. These are key factors in the challenges relating to the implementation of school improvement planning in Ghanaian Junior High Schools.

Kwaah and Ampiah (2018) further observed that the key components of the SPIP were pre-determined by the Ministry of Education (for example, improving access, provision of teaching and learning materials, school management, examination, INSET, school facilities, transportation, sanitation, and minor repairs). Hence, there was very little variation in the way schools allocated funds for the improvement of school performance. Additional challenges identified by Kwaah and Ampiah during the preparation and implementation of the SPIP were difficulty in making projections, rigidity in the plan, inadequacy of funds, and lack of transparency in the implementation. Abreh (2017) also identified weak collaboration among stakeholders in planning to improve schools in Akatsi South and Upper Manya Krobo of Ghana. Agbi, Nudzor and Agbevanu (2024) similarly found that SMCs, as prominent stakeholders in school improvement planning and implementation, were not actively involved in the planning and implementation of the SPIP. Based on the position of Agbi et al. (2024) on the role of the schools' stakeholders, among whom are SMCs, in planning and implementing school improvement programmes, the non-involvement of stakeholders is a critical issue. They held that SMCs are expected to guide the activities needed in implementing targets, identify achievements and new challenges, offer advice, assign new responsibilities, and ensure that earlier targets set in the SPIP are delivered. They must also visit schools and use participatory planning and decision-making approaches in guiding the school to implement the SPIP according to the road map drawn. Agbi et al further indicated that the functions of SMC at the implementation stage of the SPIP include contacting headteachers and/or teachers for financial and school reports on the achievements of the SPIP,

supervising and inspecting the implementation of the SPIP, and generating a progress report/observation on the SPIP activities. These are the expected roles, but they were found not to be operational according to the study by Agbi et al. (Agbi et al., 2024).

Furthermore, in a study to identify the barriers hindering the implementation of school-based health programs in Ghana, Gyasi, Zhou, Chen, Numawoseh and Opoku-Agyemang (2024), found resource constraints; lack of adequate parental and community participation, lack of adequate collaboration between stakeholders' management and leadership issues, and governance and political issues, as key obstacles to the effective implementation of the programme. Similarly, Bore and Triegaardt (2022) investigated the practise and problems of school improvement programme implementation, associated weak implementation with a low level of engagement of teachers, leaders, and parents in planning and executing school improvement plans. These studies are very significant to this current study in the sense that they highlight some of the key impediments to the successful implementation of school improvement programmes in Ghanaian Junior High Schools.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

The methodology section has been structured into six parts comprising research design, population and sampling, instrumentation, data collection procedures, data analysis procedures, and trustworthiness. Additionally, I have demonstrated how the case study design has been implemented at these stages to answer the research questions.

Research design

The study adopted a qualitative research approach, designed to address scientific and practical issues in society through naturalistic and interpretative methods, as opined by Taherdoost (Taherdoost, 2022). Aligned with this approach, a case study design, hinged on the interpretivist philosophical position, was adopted for its in-depth exploration of people, processes, events, and programs, particularly highlighting school improvement planning and implementation practices and their inherent challenges at the school level. Case studies are employed in studies that collect descriptive data through intensive examination of an event in a particular group, organization, or situation. A case study design was adopted on the basis of its strength in showing how events occur in real life (Boodhoo & Purmessur, 2009). On these grounds, the case study became the most appropriate design for this study because school improvement planning and implementation practices and their inherent challenges at the school level should be well-grounded in real-life experiences of education stakeholders. Such experiences, in their raw form, have been refined through an intensive discussion to provide a sound narrative on school improvement planning and implementation in Ghanaian Junior High Schools.

Population and sampling

The study's population entailed Headteachers (HT), Teachers (T), School improvement support officers (SISOs), School Management Committee Chairpersons (SMCs), and a Planning Officer (P.O) from Gomoa Central district in Ghana. The investigation was conducted in five schools selected from each of the five circuits in the district. A total of five teachers, five headteachers, five SISOs, three SMC Chairpersons, and a Planning Officer were included in the study. The selection of the five SISOs ensured representation from different circuits, and in each school, the headteacher and a teacher were sampled using the maximum variation variant of purposive sampling. The three SMC Chairpersons were sampled from the five selected schools. There was only one Planning Officer in the district, and so he was purposively selected, resulting in a total sample size of 19. The chosen sample size was deemed appropriate, following Boddy's (2016) position that even a sample size as small as one could be warranted in a case study. Employing a maximum variation purposive sampling technique, the participants were heterogeneous, augmenting the study's relevance (Crossman, 2023).

Instrumentation

Instruments for data collection included semi-structured interview guides, separately designed for headteachers, SMC chairpersons, SISOs, and the planning officer. These guides, featuring 12 items for headteachers, 6 for teachers, 4 for SISOs, 10 for planning officers, and 10 for SMC chairpersons, were crafted to address research questions on perspectives regarding school improvement planning and implementation practices and their inherent challenges (Cohen & Crabtree, 2006). A semi-structured interview guide was considered appropriate for this study due to the element of flexibility, which allows researchers to have a better understanding of the perspective of the interviewees (Daymon & Holloway, 2002). To have the opportunity to refocus the questions, or probe for more information, especially if something interesting emerged (Baškarada, 2014), I considered semi-structured interview guides to be appropriate in this qualitative study.

Data collection procedures

Data collection began with securing official access to schools through permission letters sent to the district education directorate. Once approval was obtained from the district education directorate, participants were contacted for interview appointments. The interviews were conducted over 4 days, involving six participants from three schools on day one (3 headteachers and 3 teachers), four participants from two schools on day two (2 headteachers and 2 teachers), five

participants on day three (SISOs), and four participants on day four (3 SMC chairpersons and 1 Planning Officer). Approximately, each interview lasted for 30 minutes. A pre-interview briefing document, outlining the study's purpose, the use of audio recording, assurance of confidentiality, and participants' freedom to participate or withdraw, was provided and read before interviews commenced. The use of audio recording conformed with Cohen and Crabtree's (2006) recommendation for subsequent transcription and analysis.

Trustworthiness

Trustworthiness or rigor of a study refers to the degree of confidence in data, interpretation, and methods used to ensure the quality of a study (Connelly, 2016). Guba (1981) advanced four criteria to enforce the trustworthiness of qualitative studies: Credibility, Transferability, Dependability, and Confirmability. Collectively, these procedures ensure the internal and external validity of qualitative studies. Commenting on the various trustworthiness criteria, Lincoln and Guba (1985) stated that credibility is confidence in the truth of the study. Transferability demonstrates the applicability of the findings in other contexts. Dependability demonstrates that the findings are consistent and could be repeated. Confirmability is the degree of neutrality of the researcher and how findings represent the views of respondents.

Furthermore, Guba and Lincoln (1989) identified “member checking” as a critical technique for ensuring credibility. By engaging in respondent validation of the data or member checking, I endeavored to satisfy the credibility criterion. Furthermore, as part of measures to ensure the trustworthiness of a qualitative study, researchers provide detailed transcription, a systematic plan, and coding (Gunawan, 2015). This principle guided my efforts as I applied a systemic coding procedure guided by Miles' (1994). Also, by presenting verbatim responses, I strengthened the confirmability criteria. In meeting the requirement of transferability, the findings of the study have been clearly presented in such a way that they could be understood or applied in other contexts. In meeting the dependability criteria, a detailed description of the procedures followed in conducting this study was provided in the methodology section.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

Thematic analysis of data was undertaken manually, adopting Miles's (1994) approach, starting on the first day after interviews. Miles' approach involved listening, transcribing, cleaning, coding, developing categories and patterns, and ultimately deriving themes. Data, in this study, refers to the direct responses from the participants transcribed from the audio recordings. This data was taken through the thematic analysis procedure to come up with the findings. The themes were illustrated with verbatim examples from the data to enhance trustworthiness. Several steps were taken to ensure the study's trustworthiness, including piloting interview guides in a different district, respondent validation, and adherence to standard ethical practices, encompassing official access, consent-seeking, and pseudonym application. All these efforts collectively enhanced the robustness of the study.

5. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the central ideas in the data that are directly related to the research questions are presented. These ideas are illustrated with verbatim examples from the data and explained in the light of other findings and in relation to existing literature on the subject to establish harmony in the study. The findings and discussions are presented with the two research questions as guides.

What is the nature of school improvement planning and implementation in Ghanaian Junior High Schools?

The first research question was focused on exploring the nature of school improvement planning and implementation in Ghanaian schools. “Nature” in this context refers to how schools plan and implement, and the contexts of their planning and implementation of school improvement programmes. Two themes: the nature of school improvement planning and the nature of school improvement implementation, emerged from the data. With regard to planning, the data centred on autonomy in planning, core areas in school level planning, steps in school level planning, and preparation of the SPIP as sub-themes were discussed. With regard to implementation, the data primarily centred on sub-themes such as the role of implementors in planning, steps in school level implementation, stakeholder commitment to implementation, and school level implementation strategies. The two themes, with their sub-themes, are discussed below:

Nature of School Improvement Planning

In this section, the effort was directed at exploring the experiences of schools in school improvement planning. It was believed that the effectiveness of planning depended to a large extent on the level of autonomy involved in the entire process.

Autonomy in planning

At the school level, headteachers played key roles in school improvement planning. However, they did not possess the needed autonomy to plan. Autonomy, therefore, became an important issue because it influenced the quality of the plan. On the headteacher level of autonomy in planning, a participant had this to share:

I am not autonomous because every decision I make with other stakeholders is guided by the rules and regulations of Ghana Education Service. Usually, I need to take into consideration what the government says about what we can do and what we cannot do as headteachers. If I always have to consult my immediate superior at the GES office in every major decision I make and sometimes even smaller ones, then where is my autonomy (HT 5- SCH 5).

A similar view was expressed by another participant:

I do not have full autonomy to make decisions. There are a number of stakeholders that I need to consult for their approval on certain decisions. My school is a unit school, so I usually consult the church and since we are also under government, I do consult the directorate for permission. If I do not get permission from these people, I do not think I have the power to initiate any major programme (HT 3- SCH 3).

Headteachers were generally emphatic on the non-existence of autonomy in their planning duties. They could initiate planning but they did not have full control over what to plan. The fundamental reason for this state of affairs was the claim that headteachers always had to consult their superiors before they made major decisions about their schools. Meanwhile, Agi (2017) had observed that, for school improvement planning to achieve the desired goals, there was a need for governments to allow significant autonomy to reside in schools to enable school leaders to initiate school improvement plans. Agi's position seemed to suggest that autonomy was enough for schools to come up with good plans but this may not always be the case. This is because Van Der Voort and Wood (2014) had identified autonomy in South African schools with regard to school improvement planning, but they observed that their schools did not come up with good school improvement plans. So, autonomy was needed for effective school improvement planning, but it was not the sole determinant of good school improvement planning. School level planning needed more than autonomy to be good.

Core areas in school level planning

The effect of the limited autonomy was felt in the choice of core areas for school improvement planning. The 'core areas' refer to the aspects of the schools where resources are committed to for improvement. Thus, when Headteachers obtained the permission to plan, they certainly had to target certain key areas of the school to direct resources through the planning. School improvement planning in schools was restricted to core areas such as enrolment drive, co-curricular activities such as sports and culture, minor repairs, TLMs, and discipline. In relation to this, a participant said: "In planning, we direct attention to teaching materials and textbooks" (HT 3- SCH 3). HT 2- SCH 2 also indicated: "In our planning, we normally pay attention to core areas of our duties. We focus planning on enrolment drive, sports, school management, culture, minor repairs, and TLMs" (HT 2- SCH 2). This headteacher also expressed his opinion in these words:

Our planning here usually focusses on academic work, co-curricular activities, infrastructure and discipline. Our enrolment has increased over the years and so we need more classrooms to cater for the increasing numbers. Discipline is also a problem in this community and that is exhibited in the behaviour of the students in our school. Due to this, we spend time in our planning to devise means of maintaining discipline in the school (HT 5- SCH 5).

The data above point to enrolment drive, sports, school management, culture, minor repairs, teaching and learning resources, academic work, discipline, and co-curricular activities as the key areas that schools accessed focused school improvement planning on. These specific areas can be categorized into academic, extra-curricular activities, character formation, and infrastructure. However, headteachers did not have the permission to allocate resources to major infrastructure development in the schools. This means schools were at the mercy of the government's financial readiness in providing infrastructure in the schools.

The core areas of school improvement planning identified in the study partially aligned with the recommendations of Adelman and Taylor (2005). They had recommended five core areas that every school improvement plan should focus on. Three of their recommendations resonate with the findings of this study. They stated, among others that, every school improvement guide should (1) delineate the content of an enabling or learning supports component (2) incorporate standards and accountability indicators for each area of learning supports content (3) include an emphasis on redefining and reframing roles and functions and redesigning infrastructure to ensure learning supports are attended to as a primary and essential component of school improvement. Their report concluded that addressing barriers to learning and teaching must be made an essential and high-level focus in every school improvement planning. Moreover, this current study also found among others that schools in the accessed district focused their school improvement planning on teaching and learning resources, academic work, discipline, and infrastructure. On the other hand, the findings did not cohere with the position of Arnold (2017) that effective school improvement planning should not be devoid of a thorough analysis of school data from school self-evaluation. He indicated that such data should always include attendance, students' behaviour, outcomes of statutory assessments, examination and test results for all pupils, and then for groups of pupils. It

was found in this study that school improvement planning was not preceded by a thorough school self-evaluation. This means school improvement planning faced the danger of overlooking essential ingredients, as outlined by Arnold.

Steps in school level planning

Additionally, schools did not follow similar procedures or steps in planning and implementation. However, generally, school improvement planning followed a six-step process involving: need assessment, preliminary consideration of planning items by teachers, re-organisation of planning items by management, consultation with stakeholders on planning items, actual planning by stakeholders, and official permission to execute the plan. These steps were not followed strictly by all schools. HT 2- SCH 2 had this to say:

Our planning begins with a meeting of teachers to provide inputs or determine the areas to be covered by the plan. The inputs will then be submitted to me as the headteacher. When I receive their inputs, I discuss them with my deputies and reorganize them. We normally consider our environment and our immediate challenges, and based on them we plan accordingly (HT 2- SCH 2).

HT 3- SCH 3 also had this to add:

When I want to develop any plan, I firstly meet my management to discuss issues I have considered for planning. After discussions with my management, the ideas would be polished for further discussions at a staff meeting so that we share the vision with them. If the items are major items and we cannot take a decision at our level as staff, then we invite the PA chair and brief him on what we intend to do. He will then inform the PA executives. However, if there is the need to call all the parents then we do that. If after meeting the parents there is the need for us to put it in writing to our district office, we do that. I don't conclude the planning at my level with teachers. It is taken further. If they have any amendment, they also bring it on board (HT 3- SCH 3).

As indicated earlier, a six-step model of school-level planning has been developed. The steps are: (1) Need assessment, (2) Preliminary consideration of planning items by teachers (3) Re-organisation of planning items by management (4) Consultation with stakeholders on planning items (5) Actual planning by stakeholders (6) Official permission to execute plan. Some key characteristics of this model are that it is based on the needs of the schools, it is oriented towards collaboration, and it is linear. As a linear model of planning, it has a beginning and an end with no opportunity for linking the end to the beginning, so that a cyclical planning could be created. Nevertheless, it is a sound addition to the body of knowledge on school-level planning for improvement.

Furthermore, the six-step model of school level planning developed from the data is different structurally from the Government of Samoa's (2005) four-step process of school improvement planning. Nevertheless, three of the elements in the current model (need assessment, preliminary consideration of planning items by teachers, and consultation with stakeholders on planning items) agree with two elements of the Government of Samoa's model of school improvement planning (determination of achievable priorities and completion of a written school improvement plan).

The current model is silent on essential elements of planning, such as setting realistic targets for each priority area and determining strategies to achieve the targets. These are pivotal in the Government of Samoa's model but are missing in the current model, calling for the need for a review which will encompass the elements of both models. This new model is hereby presented as a six-step model of school level planning: (1) Determination of achievable priorities (Need assessment, Preliminary consideration of planning items by teachers, Re-organisation of planning items by management) (2) Consultation with stakeholders on planning items (3) Setting of realistic targets for each priority area (4) Development of strategies (5) Actual planning by stakeholders (6) Official permission to execute plan.

In addition, one key characteristic of this new model of school level planning is the element of stakeholder collaboration. The inclusion of this element in the model is consistent with the position of Thompson (2018), who emphasized the importance of broader stakeholder consultation in school improvement planning. Thompson argued that comprehensive stakeholder involvement is the first fundamental of effective school improvement planning and that it is only through comprehensive stakeholder involvement that a school can undertake a responsive and context-sensitive prioritization of needs. Similarly, Mekango (2013) had argued that shared responsibility and decision-making were the cornerstones of successful planning.

Preparation of the SPIP

Knowledge about the preparation of the SPIP will inform readers on the quality of the planning done in schools studied. It provided the context for ascertaining how school level planners adhered to the planning processes they had claimed to be following in their submissions. A participant had this to say:

The SPIP is mainly done by the Finance and Administration officer and the Budget Officer. They always develop the SPIP with the Headteachers. They usually call a meeting here with the heads and give them the

template and take them through development of the SPIP. After collecting the template, they will have to go back and prepare the SPIP with the necessary stakeholders. They will be invited a second time in a workshop at the office to examine the SPIP prepared by each of them. The costing of the items will be carefully scrutinized before approval. The costs may be reviewed if found to be too high. If a headteacher does something outside the approved SPIP, he or she may have to finance it from his or her personal resources because the SPIP comes with its own money, that is the capitation grant or the GALOP fund (PO).

He added further:

.... So, when it is done, these items are put together. And when it comes to the district office, we have a schedule officer who is at the Finance and Administration Department. The schedule officer will have to go through the vetting of the SPIP which is the main planning document the schools usually submit to the directorate (PO).

The preparation of the SPIP involved a number of stakeholders (teachers, SISOs, parents' association, and the SMC) with headteachers as leaders in this regard. Headteachers and teachers actually designed the SPIP and presented it to the enumerated stakeholders for scrutiny and first approval at the school level. The planning items were determined by the headteacher with his/her teachers. The school had the liberty to select from a predetermined list of items received from the office. Headteachers and teachers were not permitted to select items outside the official items. The Capitation Grant and the GALOP fund, which were meant to finance the SPIP, were meant for only items on the SPIP template received from the district. Any headteacher who decides to insert an extraneous item must be ready to finance that from sources other than the Capitation Grant and the GALOP fund. Each of the items on the list from the district reflected the policy direction of the district for the schools. This was also a means of establishing harmony and coordination in the activities of schools in the district.

After its preparation, the stakeholders had to authenticate the document by appending their signatures to it before its submission to the district for final approval. The document would be ready for submission to the office (Finance and Administration Department) only after the SISO had scrutinized and signed it as the last assessor at the school level. This is evident in the following statement: "...before they submit it to the Finance and Administration unit at the office, they will have to bring it to me for scrutiny. I will only append my signature to it when I find that the items are all achievable" (SS-4).

The SPIP would only be submitted to the office on invitation by the Finance and Administration officer and the Budget Officer. Before this invitation, the headteachers, in a workshop, should have been taken through training on the preparation of the SPIP. It was at this training that headteachers were given the SPIP template. When the headteachers were invited a second time to the office, each headteacher was expected to come with a prepared SPIP approved by the SISO and other relevant stakeholders. At this meeting, the schedule officer at the Finance and Administration Department advised headteachers on the costing of the items on the SPIP for adjustment where necessary. By this, the schedule officer got all SPIP documents vetted. It was after vetting and approval by the schedule officer, Finance and Administration Officer, and the Budget Officer that the SPIP would become a working document for individual schools.

A careful reflection on the preparation of the SPIP unearthed the following facts: that planning within the context of the preparation of the SPIP was collaborative and systematic. Furthermore, the claim of limited autonomy earlier indicated is clearly evident in the preparation of the SPIP. Relating the preparation of the SPIP to the six-step planning model developed in this study, it could be posited that the process is not strictly in line with the model. For example, planning through the SPIP missed certain essential elements of planning, such as setting realistic targets for each priority area and determining strategies to achieve the targets. However, in terms of consultation with stakeholders and official permission to execute the plan, they were, to some extent, adhered to in the preparation of the SPIP.

Nature of School improvement implementation

This theme is centred on how schools implemented school improvement plans in the selected district. In exploring this, stakeholder roles in planning and commitment to implementation, steps in school level implementation, and school level implementation strategies became pivotal issues to be explained in answering the research question adequately. Together, they sum up how schools implemented their school improvement plans from the perspectives of the participants of this study.

Stakeholder role in planning and commitment to implementation

School level planning was not done by a single individual and therefore, implementation would also be a group affair. Hence, to explore how implementation was done by multiple actors, it was important to assess their roles and level of commitment in order to put planning and implementation in schools in the district, in their rightful context. In relation to this, HT 2- SCH 2 commented:

Implementers of school improvement plans take active part in the planning process. I cannot do the

planning alone, I am not even permitted to do that. I plan with my teachers, SISO, SMC and PTA and it is these same people that we implement plans with. They play active role in both planning and implementation (HT 2- SCH 2).

From the response above, it is evident that school level implementation was done by active players in the planning process. This is a positive sign of implementation since implementers usually succeed when they implement plans they can call their own. The implementers (mostly teachers, SISOs, SMC, and PA) were given the opportunity to make inputs into the plan which facilitates implementation of the plan at the school level. The inputs of teachers in particular, usually came in the form of committee proposals which were factored into the plan. A participant noted:

Teachers are put into committees to implement our plans. We have the Academic Committee, SHEP Coordinators, Sanitation Officers, Project and Maintenance Officers. Any plan that comes under these areas such people will see to the implementation and report back to me. In ensuring successful implementation of our plans, I embark on monitoring and evaluation of how the plan is being implemented (HT 1- SCH 1).

This finding is in line with Odei-Tetty (2021), who emphasized that the habit of playing down the implementation stage in the planning process is the reason why several public policies have failed. He noted that this usually happened when implementers are excluded from the planning process. Fortunately, implementers of school improvement plans in the schools studied were active players in the planning process.

Furthermore, implementation usually becomes successful when stakeholders are committed to the implementation. The following responses provide information on stakeholder commitment to the implementation of school improvement plans in the schools studied:

Teachers and SISOs are doing well in terms of their commitment. The commitment level of the SMC Chairperson is low. He is usually interested in signing of documents. But when it comes to the execution of the plan, you will call and call without any response. I will rate the involvement or commitment of my PTA and SMC at 45 percent. It is on two or three occasions that the SMC and PTA chairmen have sat in our locally initiated planning (HT 2- SCH 2).

HT 1- SCH 1 also commented:

The PTA Chairman is always with us but not the SMC Chairman. I will say some of the stakeholders are showing commitment while others are not. Sometimes, when we go to the chiefs for assistance, they turn us down. The assembly member is not committed to the affairs of the school (HT 1- SCH 1).

SMC 2-SCH 3 observed further:

I will say my teachers are doing very well when it comes to implementation of plans just that my people, I mean, the parents find it difficult to understand them. For me because of my work, time is a problem, but I still try my best to make some time for the school. But I must say that most of the work is done by the teachers, and especially the headmistress is doing very well. She consults me most of the times on what is going on with our plans and I provide some guidance. We are still talking to the parents to show more commitment to their children's education and the programmes of the school. They think everything to be done in the school is government's responsibility (SMC 2-SCH 3).

The responses above present diversified opinions on stakeholder commitment to the implementation of school improvement plans in the schools accessed. Key stakeholders whose commitments were assessed at the school level included teachers, PA, SMC, and SISO. Teachers and SISOs were unanimously considered as active and committed to the implementation of school improvement plans. Opinions were divided on the commitment of SMC chairpersons and PA chairpersons. However, comparatively, PA chairpersons were showing more commitment to the implementation of school improvement plans than SMC chairpersons. In fact, commitment levels of SMC and PA chairpersons were, on average, low. Parents' commitment was found to be woefully inadequate. The main reasons that accounted for the low stakeholder commitment to the implementation of school improvement plans were a lack of time and a poor understanding of the government's role in education on the part of parents. This low stakeholder commitment, especially among parents, to the implementation of school improvement plans may best be explained by the observations of Thompson (2018). For him, the success of any planning initiative is dependent on the degree to which the planning process can create a sense of commonality among stakeholders to produce the collaboration necessary for success. He added that ensuring that all stakeholders feel that their inputs are equally valued and valid is critical to such an outcome. He was of the view that stakeholders usually interpret the extent of their consultation as a basis for how they are valued, and this affects their commitment to the planning and implementation process. Judging from these assertions of Thompson, it could be posited that the nature of stakeholder engagement in the schools studied could be a contributing factor to the low commitment, aside from the lack of time and poor understanding of the government's role in education, on the side of parents, identified

in this study as reasons for the low commitment of parents in particular.

Furthermore, the study of Mekango (2013) in Ethiopia made a similar finding when he discovered that the contribution of stakeholders for effective implementation of the school improvement programme was not adequate. He found that the provision of technical support by Woreda education office, cluster supervisors, PTA, and Kebele Education and Training Board members was not adequate to support the implementation of the school improvement programme. He highlighted further that, because of the weak stakeholder roles in the implementation of the school improvement programme, not much achievement had been made with regard to the implementation of the school improvement programme. This suggests that parents, as key stakeholders in Africa, need to step up their efforts in education delivery if schools are to improve to a desirable level.

Steps in school level implementation

Furthermore, the data showed the steps followed in implementing plans in schools. Schools did not follow similar steps in implementing school improvement plans. However, from the individual steps followed in schools, a general implementation process can be derived for schools to adopt. The following responses highlight the steps in school level implementation:

We also have various committees that we work with in the school so after relaying the vision of the district director to them and bringing ours in addition, we look at the various committees and those who will work on each of the plan given. When it is about academics, we have an academic committee, so we give it to them, when it is about the health of the students, we have the SHEP (School Health Education Programme) committee, so we give it to them. We give the schedule to the committee but as time goes on the school management will be monitoring it and they will be giving us updates (HT 3- SCH 3).

Furthermore, HT 4- SCH 4 added:

With every plan, we have a facilitator who will ensure that a plan given to a committee is implemented. These facilitators are the leaders of the committees and they are answerable to the success or failure of the plan implemented by the committee. Because of that we get those people involved especially the teachers and if there is the need for any form of resource for them to use then we make sure that they have been provided so that they will do effective implementation (HT 4- SCH 4).

From the responses above, a general implementation procedure can be derived. As indicated already, schools did not follow a similar pattern of implementation of their school improvement plans. However, generally, implementation followed the following steps: (1) formation of committees (2) appointment of facilitators (3) resourcing of committees (4) coaching and monitoring. This gives a four-step model of implementation of school improvement plans. Examples of implementation committees identified were the SHEP Committee, the Sanitation Committee, the Academic Committee, Project and Maintenance Committee. For accountability purposes, facilitators are appointed as leaders of committees to oversee a committee's implementation activities. Since resources are needed to implement plans, committees were resourced with the available resources to commence implementation. In the course of implementation, headteachers provided coaching and supervisory services to the members of the implementation committees to ensure a successful implementation. One remarkable observation from the data is that the implementation of school improvement plans did not follow a strict implementation routine, as it appeared quite informal, and that the four-step implementation model derived is a product of combined implementation efforts in schools, accessed but not as a universal practice followed in all schools.

This model is different from the model of Jackson, Fixsen, and Ward (2018) (usable practices; implementation teams; implementation drivers; implementation stages; and improvement cycles), but they are not without any similarity. Their five-component model offered five crucial lessons for the implementation of school improvement programmes. First, implementation presupposes an identification and adoption of a specific practice or a tested implementation framework that would guide every step in the overall implementation process. This is missing in the implementation practices identified in schools, as schools did not implement plans based on implementation frameworks. Second, implementation of school improvement programmes should not be done without a proper formation of an implementation team that is knowledgeable in whatever implementation framework is adopted for the whole exercise. This is partially similar to the implementation practice identified in schools accessed through the formation of implementation committees. Three, every implementation exercise should possess internal functions that could keep the whole exercise alive. With regard to this, appointment of facilitators, resourcing of committees, coaching, and monitoring, which formed part of the implementation practices in schools accessed, could be interpreted as implementation drivers mentioned by Jackson et al. The fourth and the fifth can be stated together. Thus, when adequate preparation is made, the actual implementation will have to begin, and as this is done, evaluation will have to take place to assess the whole process to determine the level of adherence to the goals set initially. These last elements are also missing in the implementation practices of the schools accessed. This

means schools in the district need to formalize their implementation practices to really benefit from them.

School level implementation strategies

This theme is focused on strategies employed by stakeholders of the schools in getting their school improvement plans implemented. Strategies here imply the measures taken by heads of school to get their plans implemented amidst all odds. In relation to this, HT 2- SCH 2 had this to say:

My strategies for implementation are scale of preference and motivation. We do not have resources to implement all that we set out to do. We therefore have to settle on the pressing needs. In terms of motivation, I provide refreshment during executive meetings to the stakeholders during PLC and the preparation of the SPIP. I have realized that, because of the motivation, teachers show much commitment when it comes to implementation of our plans (HT 2- SCH 2).

A participant also had this to say: “My strategy is inclusion, and it is working” (HT 5- SCH 5). Furthermore, this participant expressed his strategy in the following words:

The strategies are monitoring and supervision and the use of staff responsibility chart. Through the Staff responsibility chart, a teacher gets to know what he or she is supposed to do. It is through that chart that we are able to implement our plans (HT 1- SCH 1).

From the responses above, a number of implementation strategies have been identified as being employed in schools accessed. The strategies employed by headteachers included scale of preference, motivation, inclusion, monitoring and supervision, and responsibility chart. Because of the inadequacy of funds, some headteachers implemented plans that responded to pressing needs (scale of preference). Headteachers believed that motivation led to stakeholder commitment to implementation. The inclusion strategy also brought a number of teachers on board to help in the implementation of plans. As implementers were monitored and supervised, implementation errors were reduced, leading to successful implementation. Through the staff responsibility chart, teachers, as primary implementers, were constantly reminded of their responsibilities in the implementation of plans in the schools. These strategies appear quite informal, though they are expected to be an integral part of school improvement plans developed by schools in the accessed schools. As indicated in the document of the Government of Samoa (2005), implementation strategies are to be determined during the planning stage, specifically at the third stage of their planning model. Yet, the implementation strategies highlighted by participants in this study appear to be afterthoughts or personal ad-hoc measures by headteachers to get their plans implemented, and so were not structured. Meanwhile, implementation strategies need to be more structured.

Challenges in planning and implementing school improvement programmes

Planning and implementation, whether initiated by an individual or a group, come with their own challenges determined by the context of the exercise. The challenges associated with the planning and implementation of school improvement programmes highly impact on the effectiveness of the programmes. In view of this, the challenges had to be explored, as knowledge of them could direct the paths of school level planners and implementers of school improvement programmes. Six main challenges of school improvement planning and implementation were identified in the data, namely, (1) Lack of transparency in financial administration (2) Differences in stakeholder backgrounds (3) Lack of consensus (4) Limited understanding of stakeholder responsibilities, (5) Weak stakeholder relationship, and (6) Delay in implementation due to lack of funds. Each of these challenges is discussed below:

Lack of transparency in financial administration

Transparency is a major ingredient in every collaborative effort towards effective school improvement planning and implementation. Stakeholders in schools need to be transparent to each other, especially in terms of financial administration, to facilitate effective and collaborative school improvement planning and implementation. The data showed a lack of transparency in financial administration in some of the schools accessed. This lack of transparency obviously impacted the level of collaboration among stakeholders in planning and implementing school improvement programmes at the school level. A participant expressed this position in the following words:

We have a challenge with the preparation of the SPIP in some of our schools. Due to lack of transparency in the process, I refuse to sign it sometimes. The process of cashing the money sometimes does not follow due process. Some headteachers, upon assistance from the directorate were able cash the Capitation Grant without other signatories. But at the normal circumstance, the SISO is supposed to sign, then counter-signed by the SMC Chair. Some of the headteachers do not involve other stakeholders in the preparation of the SPIP. They either prepare it at their offices alone or send it home and prepare it (SS-5).

The response above displays non-collaborative atmospheres in some of the schools during the planning and implementation of school improvement programmes. It was revealed that some of the headteachers were not transparent

in the preparation and management of the SPIP. Some of them prepared the SPIP single-handedly without involving the teachers and other stakeholders at the school level. Sometimes, the SISOs who were expected to supervise the preparation and management of the SPIP at the school level were sidelined. This is a clear picture of a lack of transparency, which is a constraint to effective collaboration for school improvement planning and implementation. This means that school improvement planning and implementation in some of the schools were not done collaboratively due to a lack of transparency. This finding is similar to what Setlhodi (2020) found when she explored how shared leadership collaboration practices between SGB and SMT can improve performance. She discovered that the decision-making process was done unilaterally by the principals, thereby excluding inputs by and dialogue with other stakeholders. She said, these conduct of the principals resulted in complications with compliance because there was no shared vision, which led to the absence of buy-in. She said the feeling of disregard and lack of transparency on the side of the principals resulted in stakeholder resistance to their plans. Basson and Mestry (2019), after analyzing documents relating to the financial policies of the selected schools, found that financial management in some of the schools was not transparent. They found that SGBs had neglected to include the roles of SMTs in the finance committee in the policies. Also, there was no clear delegation of authority and responsibilities on the side of the principals with regard to financial management. Basson and Mestry found challenges relating to collaboration among stakeholders, and they attributed this to a lack of transparency in financial management.

Differences in stakeholder backgrounds

Schools are run by stakeholders with different backgrounds, orientations, and experiences. Such differences could either have a positive or a negative impact on the planning and implementation of school improvement programmes. Such differences could result from occupations, political, religious, and chieftaincy affiliations. These differences can stifle collaboration if not well managed. Stakeholders in the accessed Junior High Schools were of different backgrounds as outlined above. Their differences in background emerged as a constraint to their effective collaboration in planning and implementing school improvement programmes. The following data emphasize this theme:

Differences in the backgrounds and the way they think delay our planning process. Some of them belong to different chieftaincy factions in the community and this reflects in their behaviours during discussions at our meetings as stakeholders. Some of them belong to different political parties and that also influences their arguments at meetings. A simple issue could turn into a hot argument and propaganda will also set in to delay the whole process. They sometimes accuse themselves of bringing certain issue on board because of their party so the opponents resist (HT 2- SCH 2).

The following was shared by HT 3- SCH 3:

People express certain positions during meetings because of their backgrounds or orientations. The differences in the backgrounds of stakeholders do impact on our collaboration. Someone from a rich home will easily support a levy to do something for the good of the students. The parent from a poor background may object to that and condemn the whole decision (HT 3- SCH 3).

From the data above, stakeholders exhibited different backgrounds such as educational backgrounds, economic backgrounds, political backgrounds, and chieftaincy backgrounds. These backgrounds influenced stakeholder behaviours at meetings. For example, stakeholders belonging to different chieftaincy factions did not usually agree at meetings. Stakeholders argued differently due to their different economic backgrounds. The differences in backgrounds and ways of thinking delayed decision-making in some of the schools accessed. Moreover, the impact of stakeholder background on group decision-making or collaboration has been emphasized by Haissam (2023). He observed that one of the collaboration challenges is the difficulty in dealing with cultural differences when people from diverse areas, cultures, and values must work together to reach a common goal. For him, the differences in backgrounds and cultures can generate conflicts, especially when the values and work styles do not align. Meanwhile, in this current study, such differences sometimes generated misunderstandings at planning meetings and made collaboration difficult. Furthermore, misunderstandings also ensued as a result of a lack of understanding of issues and different political affiliations. In fact, political affiliations influenced discussions at meetings, and this sometimes led to deliberate refusal to agree on issues, thereby making collaboration difficult. These factors fuelled the lack of consensus identified as a challenge to school improvement planning and implementation in schools accessed in Ghana. Lack of consensus is discussed below.

Lack of consensus

One important condition that must exist for collaboration to take place in planning and implementing school improvement programmes is consensus. Stakeholders need to have consensus over issues to enable them to harmonize their interests for effective planning and implementation. Lack of consensus is evidence of disparity in stakeholder interests. Some JHSs experienced a lack of consensus among stakeholders, and the study has identified some of the factors giving rise to that. The data below and those under the preceding theme emphasize the lack of consensus as a challenge to school

improvement planning and implementation.

There have been a number of occasions that we could not reach consensus at our meetings. We have had to abandon certain intentions because the stakeholders did not agree. This is because, we need the support of the majority of the stakeholders to get a decision implemented. The lack of understanding or agreement among the stakeholders brings the lack of consensus. It appears some of them have different interests and since it is difficult to meet everybody's interest, there will not be a consensus (HT 4- SCH 4).

The data above present 'lack of consensus' as a challenge to school improvement planning and implementation. Lack of consensus manifested itself in disagreements at planning meetings. The result of the lack of consensus was a delay in decision-making. The causes of lack of consensus included lack of understanding, differences in interests, differences in stakeholder backgrounds, political affiliations, and chieftaincy factionalism among the stakeholders. From the data, stakeholders did not always lack understanding of issues, but they refused to understand due to the political affiliation and chieftaincy factionalism, which controlled and determined the interests to pursue at planning meetings. This situation obviously mars any collaborative effort made to improve the schools. A similar finding was made by studies (Yaro, Salleh & Arshad, 2018; Bechuke & Nwosu, 2017). Yaro, Salleh, and Arshad identified a lack of consensus as a major constraint to stakeholder engagement or collaboration in Nigerian schools. Bechuke and Nwosu found that disagreements among education stakeholders affect development in schools because focus is diverted due to personal strains and destruction. They added that disagreements could lead to loss of focus on the work at hand, which inadvertently results in poor performance.

Limited understanding of stakeholders' responsibilities

Stakeholders need to understand their key responsibilities to be able to discharge them effectively in a more collaborative manner. Stakeholders of education need to have a better understanding of educational issues to enable them to engage in collaborative relationships for effective school improvement planning and implementation. The data showed a limited understanding of the responsibilities of some of the stakeholders in the schools accessed. This limited understanding affected effective collaboration in planning and implementing school improvement programmes in the schools assessed. This theme is emphasized by the data below:

Someone is illegally developing a structure on our school land but because one of our key stakeholders is related to the developer, he is finding it difficult to address the issue. This is a clear case of lack of understanding of one's duties. He has failed to understand that there is a difference between his relationship with the developer and the discharge of his duty as a key stakeholder. This is purely the work of the executives, not the headteacher. With this, how do we make a plan regarding the protection of the school's lands when we know one of us has a special interest in the issue (HT 2- SCH 2).

SMC 1- SCH 2 also had this to add:

I would not say things are always smooth when we are planning or deciding on something. Some of us are not teachers but we are trying to support. We may not understand issues as the teachers do. The teachers find it difficult to understand us. When they bring a proposal, we normally seek explanation but they think in doing that we are proving difficult. In terms of collaboration, I will say, we are doing our best as human beings despite a few challenges (SMC 1- SCH 2)

The responses above indicate that a limited understanding on the part of stakeholders impacted school improvement planning and implementation in some Junior High Schools accessed. The data pointed to the existence of a conflict of interest among some of the stakeholders due to their limited understanding of their responsibilities in the schools. Limited understanding also sometimes led some stakeholders to engage in fruitless arguments, which delayed decision-making, thereby making collaboration difficult. Also, limited understanding made some stakeholders refuse to provide the needed assistance to schools in terms of infrastructure as they thought it was the government's responsibility to provide infrastructure in schools. "Parents also refused to help the school fix part of our roof, which was ripped off by the storm. They told us it was the government's responsibility, not theirs" (HT 4- SCH 4). Parents, for example, have exhibited limited understanding of their roles in the education of their wards under the free education policy in Ghana. They erroneously thought that since education is free in Ghanaian Junior High Schools, it is the government's duty to provide everything. In a nutshell, the phenomenon of limited understanding of stakeholders' responsibilities in schools sometimes marred the collaborative atmosphere needed for effective planning and implementation in schools. Indicators of limited understanding of stakeholders' responsibilities identified in the data included conflict of interests, fruitless arguments, and failure to provide the needed assistance to schools. Because of these, collaboration in school improvement planning and implementation was sometimes challenging, and it was a result of the phenomenon of 'limited understanding' of stakeholders' responsibilities in the schools.

Furthermore, Setlhodi (2020) had similarly argued that stakeholder collaboration suffers when some of the

stakeholders have a limited understanding of their responsibilities. This is in line with the position of Mestry and Grobler (2007) that appropriate and shared decisions can only succeed if everyone is sufficiently knowledgeable and has information available to them. Setlhodi (2020) mentioned further that limited understanding of responsibilities and limited skills of stakeholders could compromise the pursuit of collegial spirit because, for her, those stakeholders who have limited skills may not participate fully, which may lead to difficulties of implementation. Similarly, Roborife and Phasha (2010) had also identified poor understanding of stakeholder roles as a constraint to effective stakeholder collaboration.

Weak stakeholder relationship

Another theme that emerged from the data was the phenomenon of weak stakeholder relationships. This theme was considered important because stakeholder collaboration in planning and implementation of school improvement programmes thrives well when there is a cordial relationship among stakeholders. Meanwhile, interactions among stakeholders in some schools were minimal, and that weakened the needed relationship for effective stakeholder collaboration in school improvement planning and implementation. The data below emphasize this theme:

We do not have consistent interactions as stakeholders to share ideas. I do not even know the SMC chairperson. The SISO does not have one-on-one interaction with teachers. He normally meets with the headteacher when he comes around. We are far apart in terms of interactions (T3-SCH 3).

Additionally, SS-3 observed:

Some of the parents have contacts of some of our superiors and so they easily report teachers and officers when there is an issue. We cannot insist on any decision they are not comfortable with because they will just pick their phone and call people in higher positions. This dampens the spirit of other stakeholders and further weakens the expected relationship among stakeholders. Teachers normally perceive such behaviours as betrayal (SS-3).

PO also had this to add:

... some NGO went to one school and gave them uniforms, footwear, TLMs without the knowledge of the directorate and the headteacher also did not inform us. When this happens, we find it difficult to make proper need assessment of the said school and factor it into our plan (PO).

The data above expresses a number of opinions about the weak relationship between stakeholders and how that affected effective collaboration for school improvement planning and implementation in the schools accessed. The data showed that stakeholders did not have frequent interactions to share ideas about how to improve the schools. The weak relationship between teachers and SISOs resulted from frequent criticisms from SISOs. This phenomenon negatively affected the needed collaboration for effective school improvement planning and implementation. This aligns with Bore and Triegaardt (2022), who associated weak implementation with a low level of engagement of teachers, leaders, and parents in planning and executing school improvement plans. Furthermore, teacher-parent relationships in some schools were also described as weak because of parents' habit of reporting teachers to superior authorities in the district. This break in the communication channel was understood by teachers as betrayal, and this negatively affected the relationship between teachers and parents, particularly in some schools. Furthermore, the data portrayed a weak relationship between education directorates and some headteachers. Thus, some headteachers sought donor assistance from NGOs without informing the directorates. In such a situation, the directorate found it difficult to make a proper needs assessment of schools and plan accordingly. For collaboration between schools and directorates to be effective, there is a need for the sharing of information. Because the directorate needs to be properly informed on the needs of the schools for effective planning. Holding on to information on resources can negatively affect the district's action plan.

Similarly, Ahmed, Zufi and Hossen (2017) found in Bangladesh that there was no collaborative bridge between teachers and SMC on sharing information and views. In the case of Ahmed et al. (2017), the fractured collaboration was as a result of the authoritarian leadership style of the SMC president, who possessed much power in the management team. Roborife and Phasha (2010) described a phenomenon that represented a weaker stakeholder relationship in the schools they studied in South Africa. In their research report, parents indicated that their job responsibilities required them to leave very early in the morning and arrive home late in the evening, when school activities were over, thus making it difficult for them to participate in school-related activities. Moreover, contacts with parents, even on the phone, were a challenge since mobile phones were luxurious in such informal areas. Also, letters could not be hand-delivered due to lack of street addresses. In view of these, parents hardly received information on their wards' education as they usually arrived home at a time when children were asleep and left early in the morning when children were still asleep.

Delay in implementation due to lack of funds

Data on this sub-theme sought to highlight the lack of funds as a factor delaying the successful implementation of school improvement programmes in schools accessed. PO had this to say:

It is very difficult to meet our timelines due to lack of funds for implementation of our programmes. We always rely on the little fund we have but it does not get us anywhere in the implementation. Due to this phenomenon, implementation of most of our programmes is delayed especially when we do not have the funds to pre-finance. Schools are not getting the expected results from the school improvement programmes implemented because the money does not come early for proper implementation (PO).

The data above indicate that stakeholders at the school level were finding it difficult to implement school improvement programmes intended to improve students' performance due to a lack of funds, which usually led to delays in implementation. When a plan or programme is delayed, its effectiveness would be compromised, and this was the case in the schools accessed. Similarly, Zickafoose et al. (2024) found that insufficient financial resources constituted a major hindrance to schools' ability to achieve results through the successful implementation of school improvement programmes. Finally, Ansah et al. (2025) also identified the inadequacy of funds as a barrier to teacher participation in CPD, which was essential for their promotion and the improvement of schools generally in Ghana.

6. CONTRIBUTION OF THE STUDY

This study provides the context for emphasizing the importance of standardized planning and implementation procedures and stakeholder engagement in school improvement programs. The development of a six-step model of school level planning: (1) Determination of achievable priorities (2) Consultation with stakeholders on planning items (3) Setting of realistic targets for each priority area (4) Development of strategies (5) Actual planning by stakeholders (6) Official permission to execute plan, makes a number of contributions. The model provides a structured framework for school-level planning pivoted on stakeholder collaboration. Additionally, it offers a practical approach to school improvement planning that can be adapted to different situational contexts in education districts.

Furthermore, the emphasis on limited autonomy and lack of stakeholder understanding as impediments to effective planning and implementation of school improvement programmes is significant for unveiling the challenging situations Ghanaian schools find themselves in as they make efforts to better their situations. Thus, the study serves a diagnostic purpose as it unearths some of the reasons for performance challenges in some Ghanaian schools. For example, the finding on limited emphasis on clear planning frameworks in schools is either enriching or initiating a debate on the need to promote effective planning regimes in Ghanaian schools through the introduction of the model mentioned above.

Policy makers in the Ghanaian education sector have enough grounds for initiating realistic measures to address school improvement challenges. Schools need more funds, and they must be properly monitored for effective disbursement of the funds. Stakeholder commitment should not be an optional role but a responsibility strongly enforced through the authority of the schools. If parents are left on their own, their commitments would always fall short of desired expectations. These ideas are all enshrined in the core points of this study.

7. IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The ultimate goal of educational leadership is to make schools more functional in the sense of repositioning schools to improve their performance. Every objective pursued in this study is connected to this goal. It has been established in this study that schools in the accessed districts have become less effective because school improvement planning and implementation were feeble. The needed collaboration to spice up the planning process has not been encouraging because the commitment level of some of the stakeholders was very low. Meanwhile, stakeholder mobilization and the need for their collaboration in schools are cherished ideals in contemporary educational leadership practices. This means educational leaders at the district and school levels have a responsibility to innovate to make schools more attractive to stakeholders. For them to achieve this, they need some level of autonomy in their professional practice as educational leaders. On the contrary, this study found headteacher autonomy in schools to be problematic. Leaders need some level of autonomy to make decisions and to innovate and bring improvement. The findings of this study on headteacher autonomy implied that educational leadership in basic schools in Ghana needs serious reforms tilted towards training and empowerment for headteachers. Training is crucial here because headteachers' leadership practices with regard to planning were not up to the expected standards.

8. CONCLUSION

The systems theory was employed as a lens to understand the interconnectedness expected among stakeholders of the school in planning and implementing school improvement programmes. This expected collaboration was found to be feeble in schools due to low stakeholder commitment to planning and implementation of school improvement programmes. Planning and implementation regimes identified in the schools accessed were below the expected standard. One of the key factors accounting for this is the limited autonomy of planners. The limited autonomy had affected the quality of planning for school improvement in Ghanaian Junior High Schools. Furthermore, the study has unearthed the need for schools to adopt systematic planning procedures, as schools were found not to be adhering to strict planning procedures. It is also important to encourage the practice of including planners in the implementation of school

improvement programmes as identified in the study.

In order for schools to experience the needed improvement, parents need to step up their efforts in the education of their wards and demonstrate much commitment. Schools also need to formalize their implementation practices and adopt best practices in planning and implementation of programmes. The government needs to reduce its influence in the planning and implementation of programmes in Ghanaian schools. This reduced influence is needed to prepare the grounds for effective stakeholder collaboration and commitment. This is because, when stakeholders own what they plan, they commit their time to its implementation.

9. REFERENCES

1. Abreh, M. K. (2017). Involvement of School Management Committees in School-Based Management: Experiences from Two Districts of Ghana. *Educational Planning*, 24 (2), 61-75. <https://docs.edtechhub.org/lib/4U4JCYGE>
2. Adelman, H., & Taylor, L. (2005). *School improvement planning: What's missing?* Center for Mental Health in Schools. Retrieved from <http://smhp.psych.ucla.edu/pdfdocs/improve.pdf>
3. Agbi, R. M., Nudzor, H. P., & Agbevanu, W. K. (2024). School management committees' knowledge and involvement in school improvement plans: implications for quality education. *Educational Planning*, 31(2), 63- 79.
4. Agi, U. K. (2017). School development planning: a strategic tool for secondary school improvement in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Journal of the International Society for Teacher Education*, 21 (1), 88- 99.
5. Ahmed, M., Zufi, A. A., & Hossen, I. R. M. S. (2017). Perceptions and challenges of collaborative leadership at secondary schools in Bangladesh. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 22(11), 19-24. DOI: 10.9790/0837-2211071924
6. Ansah, S. D., Borketey, R. B., & Kaitoo, P. (2025). Current practices and perceived benefits of continuous professional development among early grade headteachers in Adentan Municipality, Ghana. *West African Journal of Educational Sciences and Practice*, 4(1), 45-54. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17460168>
7. Armstrong, J. S. (1982). The value of formal planning for strategic decisions: Review of empirical research. *Strategic Management Journal*, 3, 197-211. DOI: 10.1002/smj.4250030303
8. Arnold, M. (2017, February 9). Effective school improvement plans [Blog post]. Retrieved from <https://www.oneeducation.co.uk/one-editorial/school-improvement/effective-schoolimprovement-plans/>
9. Baškarada, S. (2014). Qualitative case studies guidelines. *The Qualitative Report*, 19(40). 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2014.1008>
10. Basson, P., & Mestry, R. (2019). Collaboration between school management teams and governing bodies in effectively managing public primary school finances. *South African Journal of Education*, 39(2), 1-11. doi.org/10.15700/saje.v39n2a1688
11. Bechuke, A. L., & Nwosu, L. (2017). Operational dilemmas of school governing bodies in establishing school-based management in the North-West Province of South Africa. *International Journal of Sciences and Research*, 73(4):67–87. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Andre_Bechuke/publication/316458996
12. Boddy, C. R. (2016). Sample size for qualitative research. *Qualitative Market Research*, 19(4), 426-432. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QMR-06-2016-0053>
13. Boodhoo, R., & Purmessur, R. D. (2009). Justifications for qualitative research in organisations: A step forward. *The Journal of Online Education*, 1-7. <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1325607>
14. Bore, Y. H. & Triegaardt, P. K. (2022). Perception, Practices and Problems of School Improvement Program Implementation: The case of selected secondary schools in Hawassa City Administration, Ethiopia. *ICRRD Journal*, 3(3), 178-204. <https://doi.org/10.53272/icrrd.v3i3.7>
15. Broadhead, P., Cuckle, P., Hodgson, J., & Dunford, J. (1996). Improving primary schools through school development planning: Building a vision, exploring the reality. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 24(3), 277-290. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263211X98262007>
16. Clark, T. A., & McCarthy, D. P. (1983). School improvement in New York City: The evolution of a project. *Educational Researcher*, 12(4), 17-24.
17. Cohen, D., & Crabtree, B. (2006). Qualitative research guidelines project. *Technology and Investment*, 7(3). <http://www.qualres.org/HomeEval-3664.html>
18. Conley, D. T. (1993). Strategic planning in practice: An analysis of purposes, goals, and procedures. Paper presented at the annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association, Atlanta, GA.
19. Connelly, L. M. (2016). Trustworthiness in qualitative research. *MedSurg Nursing*, 25(6), 435–436. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/trustworthiness-qualitative-research/docview/1849700459/se-2>
20. Crossman, A. (2023, April 5). *Understanding purposive sampling*. [Blog post]. Retrieved from <https://www.thoughtco.com/purposive-sampling-3026727>
21. Daymon, C., & Holloway, I. (2002). *Qualitative research methods in public relations and marketing communications*. Routledge.
22. Fernandez, K. E. (2011). Evaluating school improvement plans and their effect on academic performance. *Education*

- Policy*, 25(2), 338-367.
23. Government of Samoa. (2005). *School improvement manual*. Ministry of education, sports and culture.
 24. Guba, E. G. (1981). Criteria for assessing the trustworthiness of naturalistic inquiries. *Educational Communication and Technology Journal*, 29, 75–91. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02766777>
 25. Guba, E. G., & Lincoln, Y. S. (1989). *Fourth generation evaluation*. Sage.
 26. Gunawan, J. (2015). Ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research. *Belitung Nursing Journal*, 1(1),10-11. <https://doi.org/10.33546/bnj.4>
 27. Gyasi, P. A., Zhou, L., Chen, Z., Numawoseh, E. E., & Opoku-Agyemang, A. S. (2024). Barriers to school-based health programs implementation in basic schools in Ghana: Education stakeholders' perspective, *Health Education Research*, 39(1),55–67. <https://doi.org/10.1093/her/cyad045>
 28. Haissam, A. M. (2023, March 4). 11 Top collaboration challenges: Strategies for success. [Blog post]. Retrieved from <https://theecmconsultant.com/collaboration-challenges/>
 29. Hamdan, S. M. & Fradi, G. (2023). Leadership in Continuous School Improvement: Learning and Leading to Improve. In A. Abdallah & A. Alkaabi (Eds.), *Restructuring Leadership for School Improvement and Reform* (pp. 141-158). IGI Global Scientific Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-7818-9.ch008>
 30. Huber, D. J., & Conway, J. M. (2015). The effect of school improvement planning on student achievement. *Planning & Changing*, 46(1–2), 56–70.
 31. Jackson, K. R., Fixsen, D., & Ward, C. (2018). *Four domains for rapid school improvement: An implementation framework*. National Implementation Research Network. University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill. Retrieved from <http://nirn.fpg.unc.edu/>
 32. K. O. Strunk, J. A. Marsh, S. C. Bush-Mecenas, & M. R. Duque (2016). The Best Laid Plans: An Examination of School Plan Quality and Implementation in a School Improvement Initiative. *Educational Administration Quarterly* 52(2) 259–309. DOI: 10.1177/0013161X15616864
 33. Kalman, M. (2020). School Improvement and Contextual Factors: A Qualitative Case Study on Educators' Perceptions and Experiences. *Pedagogical Research*, 5(4). doi:10.29333/pr/9134
 34. Kwaah, C. Y. & Ampiah, J. G. (2018). Implementation of the School Performance Improvement Plan in Ghana: What lessons can be learned. *The Oguaa Educator*, 12, 87-108.
 35. Levine, D. U., & Leibert, R. E. (1987). Improving school improvement plans. *Elementary School Journal*, 87, 397-412.
 36. Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Sage.
 37. Mekango, A. (2013). *Practices and challenges of implementation of school improvement program in secondary schools of Metekel Zone* (Master's thesis). Department of Educational Planning and Management. Jimma University.
 38. Mestry, R., & Grobler, B. (2007). Collaboration and communication as effective strategies for parent involvement in public schools. *Educational Research and Review*, 2(7):176–185. <https://doi.org/10.5897/ERR.9000071>
 39. Meyers, C. V., & VanGronigen, B. A. (2019). A lack of authentic school improvement plan development. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 57(3), 261–278. DOI: 10.1108/JEA-09-2018-0154
 40. Miles, M. B. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook*. Thousand Oaks.
 41. Odei-Tetty, K. (2021). *Policy and society: New directions for policy analysis with a lustre from educational policies*. Yamens Press Limited.
 42. Roborife, M. M., & Phasha, N. (2010). Barriers to school-family collaboration at a school located in an informal settlement in South Africa. *Cypriot Journal of Educational Sciences*, 5(2), 84-93.
 43. Setlhodi, I. I. (2020). Collaboration practices between the two tiers of school leadership in eradicating underperformance. *South African Journal of Education*, 40(3), 1- 11. <https://doi.org/10.15700/saje.v40n3a1796>
 44. Sinay, E, & Ryan, T. G. (2016). Research series on school effectiveness and school improvement: Characteristics of effective school improvement planning and key steps. (Research Report No. 16/17-04). Toronto, Ontario, Canada: Toronto District School Board.
 45. Taherdoost, H. (2022). What are different research approaches? Comprehensive review of qualitative, quantitative, and mixed method research: Their applications, types, and limitations. *Journal of Management Science and Engineering Research*, 5(1), 53-63. DOI: 10.30564/jmser.v5i1.4538
 46. Thompson, C. S. (2018). School administrators' and stakeholders' attitudes toward, and perspectives on, school improvement planning. *Educational Planning*, 25(4), 7-26.
 47. Van Der Voort, G. H., & Wood, L. (2014). Assisting school management teams to construct their school improvement plans: An action learning approach. *South African Journal of Education*, 34(3), 1- 7. doi: 10.15700/201409161046
 48. Yaro, I., Salleh, D., & Arshad, R. (2018). The constraints of education stakeholder's engagement in policy decision making in Nigeria. *ResearchGate*, 233- 241. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326624292>
 49. Zickafoose, A., Ilesanmi, O., Diaz-Manrique, M., Adeyemi, A. E., Walumbe, B., Strong, R., Wingenbach, G., Rodriguez, M. T., & Dooley, K. (2024). Barriers and Challenges Affecting Quality Education (Sustainable

Development Goal #4) in Sub-Saharan Africa by 2030. *Sustainability*, 16(7), 1-16.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su16072657>
